

TEACHER'S INTEREST IN USING BILINGUALISM AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY– SULU

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ABSTRACT

The study is a descriptive research which deals With Teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU - Sulu. It also deals with the demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of age, gender, status of appointment, and length of service, the extent of the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of psychological aspect and linguistic aspect (social, emotional, and interpersonal). It also deals with the significant difference in the extent of the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to demographic profile in terms of age, gender, status of appointment, and length of service, and the significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of psychological aspect and linguistic aspect (social, emotional, and interpersonal). The study was conducted at MSU - Sulu. The respondents of the study are the language teachers at MSU - Sulu. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents of the study. The research instrument is composed of two parts. Part I is about the demographic profile of the respondents which includes their age, gender, status of appointment, and length of service. Part II is composed of 5 statements each on psychological aspect and linguistic aspect. There are 5 levels to choose from which ranges from “affect so much” to “do not affect”. It was found that more than half of the teachers are females, matured, with permanent status, and new in service. The different aspect affects much the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU - Sulu. There is no significant difference in terms of demographic profile except in terms of age, gender, status of appointment, and length of service. There is a very high correlation among the two factors.

Keywords: *Bilingualism, Language teachers, Linguistic aspect, Psychological aspect, Teachers', Teachers' interest*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are essential in helping children learn multilingual, and as the benefits of bilingual education become more widely acknowledged, so do teachers' interest in using bilingualism. Programs for bilingual education give students the chance to become proficient in two or more languages, giving them invaluable language skills and cultural awareness. Teachers who are interested in using bilingualism typically have a strong appreciation for linguistic diversity and are aware of the benefits it offers to their students. They understand that bilingualism offers advantages in cognitive, social, and cultural domains in addition to language acquisition. A distinct set of abilities, methods, and techniques are needed to teach bilingualism in order to assist pupils in simultaneously gaining proficiency in two languages.

Many teachers are drawn to using bilingualism because they believe in the power of languages as a tool for communication and connection. They are passionate about promoting inclusivity and providing equal opportunities for all students, regardless of their language background. These teachers see bilingual education as a means to empower students to embrace their cultural heritage, develop a global perspective, and an interconnected world. Teachers also recognize the cognitive benefits of bilingualism, such as enhanced problem-solving skills, improved memory, and increased overall academic achievement. Teachers who are interested in using bilingualism often seek professional development opportunities to enhance their language proficiency and pedagogical skills. They engage in ongoing learning to stay updated on research-based practices, instructional methods, and effective strategies for supporting bilingual learners. *Teacher code-switching in bilingual classrooms: exploring pedagogical and sociocultural function*, (Hilda Cahyani, Michele de Courcy, and Jenny Barnett, 2018).

Bilingualism refers to the ability to proficiently speak and understand two languages. It is the skill of being able to communicate effectively in both languages, allowing individuals to switch between languages depending on the context or the people they are communicating with. Bilingualism can manifest in different ways, ranging from balanced bilingualism, where a person is equally proficient in both languages, to dominant bilingualism, where one language is more dominant than the other. Bilingualism is defined as a speaker's ability to use two languages for communication. Due to the complexity of its nature, Bilingualism can be acquired in various ways, such as growing up in a bilingual environment, attending bilingual schools, or actively learning a second language later in life. It is important to note that bilingualism is not limited to native speakers of two languages; it can also be achieved by individuals who learn a second language to a high level of proficiency. Exposure to two languages encourages students to develop an appreciation for the differences in cultures. Bilingualism is more than just the ability to speak more than one language — it's a multicultural approach to interpersonal interactions that can dramatically improve an individual's social skills. (Krista Byers-Heinlein and Casey Lew-Williams, 2015).

In addition to this, in Indonesia English is still admired as a foreign language. English language programs are only taught in class for almost two or three hours a week in

secondary school and high school level. English is not used as medium of communication in Indonesia. Indonesian people use Bahasa Indonesian or their mother tongue. In the past, teaching English in Indonesia was started from elementary school, even in many kindergartens children learned English. However, nowadays, the government omits English as a subject in Elementary school because English is considered as a difficult subject for children. They also believed that teaching English in early childhood will cause bilingualism which impacts the children in a negative way. (Benefits of Bilingualism in Early Childhood: “*Benefits of Bilingualism in Early Childhood: A Booster of Teaching English to Young Learners*” : (Rismareni Pransiska,2015).

In the USA, bilingualism is viewed as an effort to give an opportunity to learn a second language at a young age (King& Fogle, 2006). Many two-way bilingual education programs are growing rapidly as the explosive demand of parents who want their children being bilingual, in which both majority language and minority-language children learn two languages (Center for Applied Linguistics, 2005). It is indicate that bilingualism begins from family and perpetual with a patronize education program. Parents could start it with providing their children with video, flashcard, and books in the target language. By providing the children with plenty of input and interaction with the second language, bilingualism could proceed effectively.

Furthermore, the researcher observed that bilingualism is very effective to the students’, it is provides an opportunity to the students’ to expose themselves. And also can give positive effects on students’ cognitive abilities

Research Questions

This study was to determine the extent of teachers’ interest in using bilingualism at Mindanao State University (MSU) in Sulu during the School Years 2023-2024.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Gender; Age; Status of employment; and Length of service?
2. What is the extent of teachers’ interest in teaching Bilingualism at Mindanao state university-Sulu in terms of Psychological Aspect; and Linguistic Aspect?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of teachers’ interest in teaching Bilingualism at Mindanao state university Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Gender, Age, Status of employment, and Length of service?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The Study was conducted at Mindanao States University-Sulu, specifically among the tertiary teachers from different colleges. It is one of the most populated schools in province of Sulu. The creation of MSU-Sulu is one of the greatest educational developments in the province of Sulu. The establishment of MSU- Sulu provides the tausug chances to pursue higher education. The courses offered ranging from two year technology courses in Fisheries and Agriculture. Others are Bachelor Degree in Arts and Sciences, Agriculture, Fisheries, Education, Nursing, Public Administration and Criminology, Computer Sciences, Business Administration and Accountancy and Law Studies. Doctoral program in Philosophy is now available. Thus the tausug Professional are provided greater opportunities to improve their professional career. (Prof. Laling A. Jupakkal).

MSU-Sulu was established on February 11, 1974 that was made operational by the strength of the Board of Regents Resolution No. 860, as amended to provide a well-meaning education to the people of the ravaged province (Sulu) and this will strives to pursue the traditional function of the university such as classroom instruction, quality research, and extension program.

The respondents of the study were the tertiary teachers' of the Mindanao State university-Sulu, who are resident's teachers.

Sampling Design

The respondents of the study were one hundred (100) Teachers' of the Mindanao States University-Sulu. The researcher was use a purposive sampling procedure in the selection of the respondents. Purposive sampling is applied to ensure that the specific type of sample or case was included is part of the final sample in the study (Campbell et al., 2020).from the total population of the tertiary teachers of the Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Distribution of Respondents according to Colleges

Colleges	Total
College of Arts and Sciences	15
College of Nursing	15
College of Agriculture	15
College of Business Administration and Accountancy	15
College of Criminology and Public Affairs	10
College of Computer Studies	10

College of Education	10
College of Fisheries	10
Grand Total	100

Respondents of the Study

The research respondents were one hundred (100) teachers of the Mindanao States University-Sulu. There are two hundred eighty-one (281) Teachers’, seventy-seven (77) contractual Faculty, fifty (50) Lecturers, and one hundred fifty-four (154) Permanent. The respondents are given the survey questionnaire to determine their ideas about the teachers’ interest in teaching Bilingualism. The said respondents are distributed with regard to their field of studies. The researcher makes a distribution to easily access them.

The researcher carefully selects the teacher as their respondents to create a clear and accurate data. It is in the purpose of determining the objectives and purpose of the said research.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the collection of data, the following steps were applied:

The permit to administer the questioner was sought from the Deans of the different colleges. The launching and administering as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire were conducted personally by the researcher. The researcher organized the responses of the participants and was analyzed the data that was gather. Furthermore, the statistician was analyzed and interprets the computed data after which the results outcome was consulted to the adviser.

Research Instrument

The survey questionnaire was used in this study was adopted from “Cultural Responsive Teaching theory” which was developed by Geneva Gay, 2000. And consists of two parts. Part I was focused on the demographic profile of the respondents that includes the Gender, Age, Status of Employment, and length of service. Part II was on the extent of teachers’ interest in teaching bilingualism at Mindanao State University-Sulu.

The data was obtained using the questionnaire was analyzed through 4-point Likert Scale such as 1=strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= Agree, 4= strongly agree.

The researcher first submitted the adopted questionnaire to her thesis adviser for possible correction and suggestions. The research questionnaire was adapted from

Cultural Responsive Teaching theory which was developed by Geneva Gay, 2000. However, to suit its applicability with the setting of the present study, a slight modification was made, for perusal of at least two (2) experts from among the faculty members at School of Graduate studies at Sulu State College.

For the Statistical treatment of data, the researcher was used the Frequency and Percentage to identify the demographic profile of the Teachers' respondents of the Mindanao State University-Sulu. For statement number 2, to determine the extent of teachers' interest in teaching Bilingualism at Mindanao state university-Sulu. In research question number 3, weighted mean was used to determine the extent on Teachers' interest in teaching bilingualism at Mindanao State University –Sulu. While T-test was used to for independent samples and one –way ANOVA analysis of variance to ensure if there is a significant differences in the extent of Teachers' Interest in Teaching Bilingualism at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are group according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, employment status and length of service.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The researcher only confirmed her study on the Teachers' interest in teaching bilingualism at Mindanao State University-Sulu who are teachers'. The researcher used purposive random sampling to get one hundred (100) respondents from each college namely, College of Art and Sciences (CAS), College of Nursing (CON), College of Agricultural (COA), College of Business administration and Accountancy (CBAA), College of Criminology and Public Affairs (CCPAC), College of Computer Studies (CCS), College of Education (COED), and college of Fisheries (COF). There will be also gathered data on the views, problems and difficulties and observation and development of the Teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism.

RESULTS

1. What is the demographic profile of the teachers at Mindanao State University – Sulu in terms of 1.1 gender, 1.2 age, 1.3 status of appointment, and, 1.4 length of service?

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender.

The result implies that 66 or 68.8% of the respondents are males and only 30 or 31.2% are females.

The result implies that more than half of the respondents are males

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	66	68.8%

Female	30	31.2%
TOTAL	96	100%

1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. It showed that 27 or 28.1% of the respondents of the study are 25 years old and below and only 8 or 8.3% are between 41 – 45 years old. Other age bracket shows at 20% in number. The result implies that those 25 years old and below represents the majority among the age brackets and only a few are between 41 – 45 years old in terms of gender.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
25 years old and below	27	28.1%
26 – 35 years old	21	21.9%
36– 40 years old	20	20.8%
41 – 45 years old	8	8.3%
46 years old and above	20	20.8%
TOTAL	96	100%

1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Status of Appointment

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of status of Appointment. It showed that 45 or 46.8% of the respondents holds a permanent status while 21 or 21.9 % are lecturers. The result implies that permanent teachers has the highest number among the

Respondents in terms of status of appointment.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Status of Appointment

Status of Appointment	Frequency	Percentage
Lecturer	21	21.9%
Contractual	30	31.3%
Permanent	45	46.8%
TOTAL	96	100%

1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of length

Of service. It showed that 46 or 47.9% of the respondents are 5 years and below only in service while only 8 or 8.3% are between 16 – 20 years in service. The result implies that almost half of the teachers' at MSU – Sulu are new in service.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
5 years and below	46	47.9%
6 – 10 years	20	20.8%
11 – 15 years	11	11.5%
16 – 20 years	8	8.3%
21 years and above	11	11.5%
TOTAL	96	100%

2. What is the extent of the teacher's interest in Using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of 2.1 psychological aspect, and 2.2 linguistic aspects (social, emotional, and interpersonal)?

Table 2.1 presents the factors affecting the teacher's interest in teaching Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of psychological aspect.

It showed that the respondents indicated affect much in all statements in the context of psychological aspect. Among those statements are; I feel confident in my ability to assess and evaluate bilingual students (mean = 3.180, SD = .680); I believe that teaching bilingualism is valuable and beneficial for students (mean = 3.060, SD = .927); and I believe it's crucial to educate bilingual students for both academic and personal development (mean = 3.050, SD = .933). The average mean of 3.052 means that the factors affect much the teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of psychological aspect.

The result simply implies that the psychological aspect does affects the teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

Table 2.1 Extent of the Teacher's Interest in Using Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of Psychological Aspect

Psychological Aspect	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I believe that teaching bilingualism is valuable and beneficial for students.	3.060	.927	Affect Much
2. I believe it's crucial to educate bilingual students for both academic and personal development.	3.050	.933	Affect Much
3. I recognize the advantage of bilingual education for students.	3.030	1.015	Affect Much
4. I have the access to the materials and tools to teach bilingual students.	2.940	.982	Affect Much
5. I feel confident in my ability to assess and evaluate bilingual students.	3.180	.680	Affect Much
AVERAGE	3.052		AFFECT MUCH

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
4	3.50 – 4.49	Affect So Much
3	2.50 – 3.49	Affect Much
2	1.50 – 2.49	Affect Less
1	1.00 – 1.49	Do Not Affect

Table 2.2 presents the factors affecting the teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in terms of linguistic aspect as to social. The result showed that the respondents indicated affect much in all statements and Among these are; I believe the value and recognition of bilingualism in society impact teacher's interest in teaching it (mean = 3.310, SD = .529); I believe teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism can be increased or sustained (mean = 3.260, SD = .603); and I believe that teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism has an impact on student's language development and academic (mean = 3.180, SD = .632). The average mean of 3.186 means that the factors affect much the teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

Table 2.2 Extent of the Teacher's Interest in Using Bilingualism in terms of Linguistic Aspect as to Social

Social Aspect	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I have personal experience or background influence and interest in teaching bilingualism.	3.040	.739	Affect Much
2. I have encountered challenges or barrier in bilingualism that have affected or sustained my interest.	3.140	.705	Affect Much
3. I believe teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism can be increased or sustained.	3.260		Affect Much

		.603	
4. I believe that teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism has an impact on student's language development and academic.	3.180	.632	Affect Much
5. I believe the value and recognition of bilingualism in society impact teacher's interest in teaching it.	3.310	.529	Affect Much
AVERAGE	3.186		AFFECT MUCH

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
4	3.50 – 4.49	Affect So Much
3	2.50 – 3.49	Affect Much
2	1.50 – 2.49	Affect Less
1	1.00 – 1.49	Do Not Affect

Table 2.3 presents the extent of the factors affecting the teacher's interest in using bilingualism in terms of linguistic aspect as to emotional.

The respondents indicated affect much in all statements. Some of these statements are; I believe teaching bilingualism can motivate the students to enhance their cognitive abilities (mean = 3.440, SD = .577); I believe every teacher's individual multilingual skill plays in their enthusiasm for teaching bilingualism (mean = 3.280, SD = .610); and I believe collaborating with other teachers who are also interested in teaching bilingualism can enhance students' linguistic abilities (mean = 3.250, SD = .649). The average mean of 3.286 means that the emotional aspect affects much the interest of teacher's in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

The result simply implies that emotional aspect affects most of the time the interest of teachers in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

Table 2.3 Extent of the Teachers' Interest in Teaching Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu as to Emotional

Emotional Aspect	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I believe every teacher's individual multilingual skill plays in their enthusiasm for teaching bilingualism.	3.280	.610	Affect Much
2. I understand teacher perception of student's outcomes and success in bilingual education influence their interest in teaching.	3.210	.724	Affect Much
3. I believe the overall school climate culture influence teacher interest in the teaching of bilingualism.	3.250	.632	Affect Much

4. I believe teaching bilingualism can motivate the students to enhance their cognitive abilities.	3.440	.577	Affect Much
5. I believe collaborating with other teachers who are also interested in teaching bilingualism can enhance students' linguistic abilities.	3.250	.649	Affect Much
AVERAGE	3.286		AFFECT MUCH

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
4	3.50 – 4.49	Affect So Much
3	2.50 – 3.49	Affect Much
1	1.50 – 2.49	Affect Less
1	1.00 – 1.49	Do Not Affect

Table 2.4 presents the extent of the factors affecting the teacher's interest in using Bilingualism in terms of linguistic aspect as to interpersonal.

The respondents indicated affect much in all statements. Some of these statements are; availability of resources and materials for using bilingualism (mean = 3.350, SD = .725); personal interest and proficiency in multiple languages (mean = 3.320, SD = .688); and recognition of the benefits of bilingualism for students learning (mean = 3.290, SD = .767). The averages mean of 3.242 means that the interpersonal aspect affects much the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

The result simply implies that interpersonal aspect often affects the teacher's interest in Using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

Table 2.4 Extent of the Teacher's Interest in Using Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu as to Interpersonal

Interpersonal Aspect	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Personal interest and proficiency in multiple languages.	3.320	.688	Affect Much
2. Recognition of the benefits of bilingualism for students learning.	3.290	.767	Affect Much
3. Professional development opportunities and training in bilingual education.	3.040	.845	Affect Much
4. Support from colleagues and school administration.	3.210	.870	Affect Much
5. Availability of resources and materials for teaching bilingualism.	3.350	.725	Affect Much
AVERAGE	3.242		AFFECT MUCH

LEGEND

SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
4	3.50 – 4.49	Affect So Much
3	2.50 – 3.49	Affect Much
1	1.50 – 2.49	Affect Less
1	1.00 – 1.49	Do Not Affect

- Is there a significant difference in the extent of the teacher's interest in Using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender, age, status of appointment, and length of service?

3.1 By Gender

Table 3.1 shows the differences in the extent of the teacher's Interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to gender. The t-test was used for gender since there are only two categories. The sig. value of 0.240 for psychological aspect is greater than the p = value at .05. and the sig. value of 0.354 for linguistic aspect is greater than the p – value at .05. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference in the extent of the factors affecting the teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to their gender.

The result implies that gender is not a determinant on the teacher's interest in Using Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu.

Table 3.1 t – test for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Teacher's Interest in Using Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in terms of Gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	t	Sig.	Description
Psychological Aspect	Male	4.350	.630	.190	27.599	.240	Not Significant
	Female	4.160	.750				
Linguistic Aspect	Male	3.750	.550	.130	28.250	.354	Not Significant
	Female	3.880	.720				

Table 3.2 ANOVA for Significant Difference in the Extent of the Teacher's Interest in Using Bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in terms of terms of Age, Status of Appointment, and Length of Service

	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	f	Sig.	Description
Age						

Between Groups	2.954	4	.739	.854	.495	Not Significant
Within Groups	78.671	91	.865			
TOTAL	81.625	95				
Status of Appointment						Not Significant
Between Groups	.128	2	.064	.074	.930	
Within Groups	80.609	93	.867			
TOTAL	80.737	95				
Length of Service						Not Significant
Between Groups	3.780	4	.945	1.144	.371	
Within Groups	75.121	91	.826			
TOTAL	78.901	95				

Table 3.2 presents the significant difference in the extent of the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in terms of terms of age, status of appointment, and length of service.

The sig. value of 0.495 for age is greater than the p = value at .05, the sig. value of 0.930 for status of appointment is greater than the p – value at .05, and the sig. value of 0.371 is likewise greater than the p – value of .05. It means that the null hypothesis is accepted. There are no significant differences in the extent of the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu when data are grouped according to their age, status of appointment, and length of service.

The result implies that the different demographic profiles of the teacher's at MSU–Sulu cannot predict the extent of the effect of their interest in using bilingualism.

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the teacher's interest in using bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of psychological aspect and linguistic aspect??

Pearson Product – Moment Correlation or Pearson r was used to determine if there is a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of the teachers' interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU – Sulu in the context of psychological aspect and linguistic aspect?

Table 4. Significant Correlation in the Teachers' Interest in Using Bilingualism at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the context of psychological aspect and linguistic aspects

		Pearson r	Sig.	n	Description
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Psychological Aspect	Linguistic Aspect	.812	.000	96	Very High
Linguistic Aspect	Psychological Aspect	.897	.000	96	Very High

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha = .05$

Correlation Scales adapted from Hopkins (2002):

0.0– 0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1 – 0.3 = Low; 0.3 – 0.5 = Moderate; 0.5 – 0.7 = High;
0.7 – 0.9 = Very High; 0.9 – 1.0 = Nearly Perfect

The value of $r = 0.812$ for psychological aspect was interpreted as very high correlation while the value of $r = 0.897$ for linguistic aspect was also interpreted as very high correlation at significant value of .05 two- tailed test.

The result simply implies that the different factors has a very high relationship as far as the extent of the effect of the factors on the teacher's interest in teaching bilingualism MSU – Sulu is concern.

Conclusions

The following was concluded based on the findings of the study:

1. Majority of the respondents are male, quite young permanent employee of the school and barely new in service.
2. The psychological aspect and linguistic aspect often affect the teachers' interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU-Sulu.
3. The demographic profile of the respondents cannot determine the significance difference on the extent of teachers' interest in teaching bilingualism at MSU-Sulu.
4. The very high correlation between the psychological aspect and linguistics aspect clearly means that both aspect are interrelated and it difficult to separate one aspect from the other aspects

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1. Teachers' handling of bilingualism at Mindanao State University-Sulu may have much-needed interest in teaching it for them to very effective.
2. The administration may support all the endeavours of teachers' handling of bilingualism in order to keep their interest alive.
3. The administration may send teachers' handling of bilingualism to relevant training and seminars related to bilingualism.
4. The language department of Mindanao State University-Sulu may strengthen their programs in teaching English, Filipino and Bilingualism.
5. Future researchers' works on the same topic may include variables not covered by the present studies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The writers have stated that they have no competing interest with respect to the investigation, writing, or release of this piece. The investigation was carried out by the writers in compliance with the protocol for research ethics. The individual taking part received informed consent before to getting the survey for the study. Data management was done. At the greatest degree of secrecy.

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